

FREE EDGE EFFECTS IN MICROBUCKLING FAILURE OF UNIDIRECTIONAL COMPOSITES

David G. Taggart
Department of Mechanical Engineering
University of Rhode Island
Kingston, RI 02881

ABSTRACT

Fiber microbuckling is generally accepted to be the dominant compression failure mode for unidirectional fiber composites. Numerous analytical models for microbuckling failure have been presented. Since microbuckling failure is a stability governed mechanism, the critical failure loads are extremely sensitive to material imperfections and non-uniformities. In particular, microstructural features such as fiber misalignment, fiber/matrix interfacial failure, matrix porosity, fiber clustering, matrix plasticity and free edge effects are all thought to significantly degrade the compression strength. In this study, the effect of fiber location relative to the free surface on microbuckling failure is examined. A 2-D numerical (finite element) approach is used to determine the critical microbuckling strain level for various configurations. It is demonstrated that the reduced lateral support of a single fiber located near the surface (as compared to that for an interior fiber) of a semi-infinite matrix significantly reduces the microbuckling strain level. When constituent properties for typical commercial composites are considered, however, single fiber microbuckling occurs at strain levels significantly higher than experimentally observed values for actual composites. Interactions with adjacent fibers tend to destabilize the structure, leading to reduced critical strain levels. To study this effect, a multiple fiber model is developed and applied to determine the free edge effect on the compressive microbuckling failure strain.

KEYWORDS: Compression; Edge Effects; Microbuckling; Finite Element Analysis; Strength

1. INTRODUCTION

In many advanced composite material structural applications, the critical mechanical property is the compressive strength. It is generally accepted that for typical unidirectional fiber composite laminates, compression failure is associated with fiber microbuckling. It is often difficult to achieve the theoretical strength expected from both theoretical models or idealized laboratory conditions in actual components. This is believed to be a due to localized defects and/or edge effects which initiate premature macroscopic structural failure. It is therefore important that the effect of material defects and associated localized failure phenomena on the macroscopic composite strength be understood. The objective of this study is to determine the effect of a

fiber's location relative to the laminate free edge on its critical buckling failure strain.

Numerous micromechanical models for compression microbuckling failure have been developed in recent years (1-17). Detailed reviews of compression behavior of composite materials are also available (17,18). Many of the analytical models are based on the early work by Rosen (10). In his analysis, Rosen models the composite as alternating layers of fiber and matrix whose thicknesses depend on the macroscopic fiber volume fractions. He identified two potential microbuckling modes, extensional (out-of-phase) and shear (in-phase), and derived analytical expressions for the critical stress associated with each mode. In general, for typical composite constituent properties and fiber volume fractions, the in-phase buckling mode occurs at smaller compressive strain levels than the extensional mode. Rosen's in-phase model yields a critical compressive microbuckling stress $\sigma_{cr} = G_m / (1 - V_f)$ where G_m is the matrix shear modulus and V_f is the fiber volume fraction. The critical microbuckling strain is given by $\epsilon_{cr} = \sigma_{cr} / E_L = G_m / [E_L (1 - V_f)]$ where E_L is the composite effective axial (fiber direction) modulus. Recent experimental studies (2,18) have demonstrated that the Rosen prediction consistently overestimates observed compression failure strains.

Rosen's model (and numerous subsequent models) assume that microbuckling is a global phenomena such that all fibers simultaneously reach a critical strain and buckle either in-phase or out-of-phase with adjacent fibers. Several researchers (1,7,8,19) have suggested that microstructural defects contribute to localized microbuckling at stress levels well below theoretical predictions for global microbuckling. In particular, defects such as fiber misalignment (or waviness), fiber/matrix debonding, matrix porosity and non-uniform fiber distributions (fiber clustering) are believed to contribute to decreased compression strength. Similarly, material nonlinearities such as matrix plasticity tend to reduce the amount of lateral support provided to the fiber and hence reduce the composite compressive strength (16,18). In addition, recent experimental studies (20,21) have shown that the compression failure process consists of an initial surface fiber buckling and subsequent propagation through the material. This result is not surprising since the surface fibers have the least amount of lateral support. It is therefore postulated that the microbuckling behavior of the surface fiber controls the compression strength of the composite.

The effect of reduced lateral support at a free-edge has been discussed in two recent papers. In a study by Waas et al (15), an analytical model was developed for a single surface fiber supported by an infinite elastic foundation. In this analysis, the fiber was modeled as a beam and the semi-infinite matrix was taken to be homogeneous and isotropic. The fiber was assumed to buckle in a sinusoidal mode shape where the buckle wavelength is taken as the length which minimized the microbuckling strain. Waas et al also presented an analysis for a semi-infinite layered composite and compared the results to that for an "infinite" composite (analogous to Rosen's model). The semi-infinite model assumes that failure initiates by surface fiber microbuckling. At the critical surface fiber buckling strain level, it is assumed that interior fibers (far from the free surface) do not buckle, leading to a microbuckle mode shape which decays (exponentially) with depth. It is shown that for cases where $V_f < 0.2$, the surface fiber buckles at a strain level significantly lower than the Rosen prediction. Surprisingly, at higher fiber volume fractions, the model which accounted for the free edge effect yields a higher microbuckling strain than the infinite composite model.

In another recent study (14), a foundation modulus approach was used to determine the surface fiber buckling strain. In this model, the foundation modulus for a cylindrical fiber was estimated in terms of the surrounding composite properties and the foundation (or specimen) thickness. It was demonstrated that increased foundation thickness reduces the lateral support for surface fibers and hence, results in lower surface fiber microbuckling failure strains. The resulting compression strength to specimen thickness relation was shown to correlate well with experimental results (2).

In the present paper, approximate analytical and numerical models are developed to study the effect of fiber position on the composite microbuckling strain. It is assumed that failure initiates due to microbuckling of a single fiber. The critical microbuckling strains for both surface fibers and interior fibers are calculated by placing a single fiber either on the free edge or far from the free edge of a thick, uniform continuum whose elastic properties are those of the matrix material. These results are correlated with Timoshenko's (22) beam on an elastic foundation model and appropriate estimates for the elastic foundation modulus are obtained. Then, the effect of increased foundation modulus due to the presence of adjacent fibers is considered in the second approach. Here, a single fiber is embedded either in the interior or on the surface of a continuum whose elastic properties are the effective composite properties. Again, it is assumed that only one fiber buckles and the effect of adjacent fibers is solely to increase the amount of lateral support. Finally, a multiple fiber model is developed to model adjacent fiber interactions on composite microbuckling.

2. FOUNDATION MODULUS APPROACH

To estimate the axial strain level associated with microbuckling of a single fiber, Timoshenko's beam on an elastic foundation analysis (22) is applied. Timoshenko gives the buckling load for a beam (fiber) of length, ℓ , elastic modulus, E_f and moment of inertia, I , resting on an elastic media with foundation modulus, β , as

$$P_{cr} = \frac{\pi^2 E_f I}{\ell^2} \left(m^2 + \frac{\beta \ell^4}{m^2 \pi^4 E_f I} \right) \quad (1)$$

where m is an integer which minimizes P_{cr} .

Application of this model requires that an appropriate estimate of β in terms of the Young's modulus (E_m) of the foundation (matrix) material and the fiber location be obtained. The foundation modulus is defined as the reaction per unit length induced by a lateral deflection of unit magnitude. The energy required to deform an element of width, b , and length, dx , of the elastic foundation by a lateral deflection of magnitude y is given by Timoshenko as $(\beta y^2/2)dx$. If the foundation is approximated as a series of columns with Young's modulus, E_m , cross-sectional area ($b dx$), and effective depth d_{eff} , then energy associated with a lateral deflection, y , would be $(E_m b y^2 / 2 d_{eff}) dx$. Hence the foundation modulus is expected to be proportional to the matrix modulus and inversely proportional to an effective foundation depth, d_{eff} .

$$\beta = \frac{E_m b}{d_{eff}} \quad (2)$$

Note that in general, the effective depth parameter is expected to be related to the fiber location relative to a free surface, the microbuckle wavelength and the matrix shear modulus.

With this estimate (Eq. 2) for the foundation modulus, the critical strain associated with fiber microbuckling can be determined. Since m is an integer which minimized P_{cr} , ℓ/m is the microbuckle half-wavelength. For a beam of rectangular cross-section, $I=bt^3/12$ where t is the beam (fiber) thickness. We define a normalized buckle half-wavelength $L=\ell/mt$ and a normalized effective foundation depth $\delta=d_{eff}/t$. Noting that P_{cr} is the load in the fiber, Eq. 1 (with Eq. 2) can be rearranged to yield the compressive strain, ϵ_{cr} , associated with microbuckling

$$\epsilon_{cr} = \frac{\sigma_f}{E_f} = \frac{P_{cr}}{b t E_f} = \frac{\pi^2}{12 L^2} + \frac{L}{\pi^2 \delta \left(\frac{E_f}{E_m}\right)} \quad (3)$$

Microbuckling occurs at the half-wavelength which minimizes ϵ_{cr} , given by

$$L = \left[\frac{\pi^4}{6} \delta \left(\frac{E_f}{E_m}\right) \right]^{1/3} \quad (4)$$

which yields the microbuckling strain

$$\epsilon_{cr} = \left[\frac{4}{3} \pi \delta \left(\frac{E_f}{E_m}\right) \right]^{-2/3} \quad (5)$$

Note that, as expected, in the limit as $E_m \rightarrow 0$ (no foundation support), the microbuckle wavelength approaches infinity and the microbuckling strain for the infinitely long fiber goes to zero.

3. NUMERICAL MODEL

The numerical approach consists of a plane stress finite element bifurcation analysis. Assuming linear material behavior, the bifurcation buckling is associated with geometric non-linearities. The general bifurcation analysis formulation given by Cook et al (23) is specialized for 2-D plane stress analysis. For accurate modeling of bending deformation with slender elements, an 8-noded isoparametric element formulation is adopted. Details of the numerical formulation are given in ref. (24).

As in Rosen's model, the numerical model idealizes the composite as a layered structure with alternating layers of fiber and matrix material. The relative layer thicknesses are determined by the composite fiber volume fraction. A uniaxial compressive strain, ϵ_0 , is applied by imposing uniform axial (y-direction) displacements, $v(x,0)=0$ and $v(x,L_m)=\epsilon_0 L_m$ where L_m is the finite element model mesh length (see. Fig. 1). Transverse (x-direction) displacements are not constrained except at one node to prevent rigid body translations. These boundary conditions force the fiber to buckle in a mode such that the mesh length is an integer multiple of the

microbuckle half-wavelength. To determine an appropriate mesh length to model microbuckling of an infinitely long fiber, a systematic procedure to vary the mesh length was devised. To facilitate this procedure, an automatic mesh generation algorithm was incorporated directly in the finite element code. In these analyses, care was taken to avoid element aspect ratios in excess of five and to include at least five elements per microbuckle wavelength.

The "natural" microbuckle wavelength for an infinite fiber was determined by first analyzing a relatively long (3-4 wavelength) mesh. Typical meshes are shown in Fig. 1 which is for the case of a single fiber embedded in the interior (Fig. 1a) and on the surface (Fig. 1b) of a thick (infinite) matrix. The microbuckle wavelength is estimated by counting the number of half-waves in the deformed mesh generated by the buckling analysis. Fig. 2 shows that for the case of $E_f/E_m=100$, the microbuckle half-wavelength normalized by the fiber thickness, L , is approximately equal to 24. The next step is to generate several new meshes with mesh lengths near the approximate wavelength. A typical single wavelength deformed mesh is shown in Fig. 2b. The mesh length which minimizes the critical microbuckling strain corresponds to the microbuckle wavelength for an infinite fiber. For the case shown ($E_f/E_m=100$), the critical strain, $\epsilon_{cr}=.0284$, occurs at a mesh length equal to 19.5 times the fiber thickness.

To model multiple fiber microbuckling, a similar approach is taken. In this case, a mesh consisting of alternating layers of fiber and matrix is considered. As discussed by Waas et al (15), for the infinite composite case, above a critical fiber volume fraction the microbuckling wavelength approaches infinity and the critical strain approaches Rosen's shear mode prediction. For this reason, in the numerical model the choice of mesh length determines the microbuckle half-wavelength. Therefore, to study multiple fiber microbuckling, several mesh lengths are analyzed to determine the limit of ϵ_{cr} as $L_m \rightarrow \infty$. Similarly, the mesh width, W_m , must be varied to determine the limit of ϵ_{cr} as $W_m \rightarrow \infty$. The two cases of interest are the infinite composite (no free edges) and the semi-infinite composite (one free edge). To model a infinite composite, a shear mode (in-phase microbuckling) is enforced by coupling the deformation of each of the fibers such that their microbuckling mode shapes are identical. Note that this coupling also prevents lateral contractions. To prevent artificial induced transverse stresses (prior to buckling), the fiber and matrix Poisson's ratios are assumed to be zero. The semi-infinite composite is modeled by coupling the deformation of interior fibers (far from the free edge) and allowing independent deformation of fibers near the surface.

4. RESULTS

At low fiber volume fractions, interactions with adjacent fibers are neglected. In this case, microbuckling failure may be analyzed by considering a single fiber embedded either at the free edge or in the interior of a very thick (infinite) matrix material. The analysis was performed at ratios of fiber to matrix modulus (E_f/E_m) between 10 and 1000.

As shown in Fig. 3, the critical strain associated with microbuckling of surface fibers agrees well with the analysis of Waas et al (15). Similarly, if one chooses (arbitrarily) an effective foundation depth of $\delta=1/2$ for surface fibers and $\delta=1/4$ for interior fibers, excellent agreement with Timoshenko's elastic foundation analysis is obtained. The corresponding microbuckle half-wavelength results (Fig. 4) agree very well with the results of Waas et al (15). The correlation with Timoshenko's elastic foundation analysis, however, is not as good. Note, however, the choice

of slightly higher effective foundation depths ($\delta \approx 0.6$ for surface fibers and $\delta \approx 0.3$ for interior fibers) yields good correlation for the wavelength result but reduces the correlation with the critical strain results. This discrepancy is thought to be due to the approximate nature of the estimate of the foundation modulus, β (Eq. 2).

It is clear from these results that surface fibers buckle at a strain level significantly lower than interior fibers. For the range of E_f/E_m considered, the surface fiber microbuckle strain is approximately 1/2-2/3 that of an interior fiber. This is due to the smaller amount of lateral support provided to the surface fiber as compared to the interior fiber.

These results suggest that Eq. 5, with appropriate estimates for the effective foundation depth, δ , may be used to estimate the critical microbuckling strain in a typical commercial composite. If interactions with adjacent fibers are neglected (i.e. for the case of dilute fiber concentrations), the foundation properties may be taken as those of the matrix material. Consider, for example, a unidirectional composite with S2 glass fibers in an epoxy matrix. Using the constituent properties given in Table 1, it can be seen that for such a composite $E_f/E_m = 24.8$. Using effective foundation depths $\delta = 1/2$ for surface fibers and $\delta = 1/4$ for interior fibers yields (Eq. 5) critical microbuckle strains of $\epsilon = 0.072$ and 0.114, respectively. The corresponding normalized half-wavelengths (eq. 5) are $L = 5.1$ and 6.3, respectively. These strain levels corresponds to fiber stress levels of 893 ksi and 1,414 ksi, respectively and matrix stress levels of 36 ksi and 57 ksi respectively. These stress levels exceed the constituent compressive strengths, suggesting that single fiber microbuckling in a dilute S2 glass/epoxy composite is not expected to be the dominant failure mechanism.

In an effort to model composites with finite fiber volume fractions, the analysis was repeated with the fiber embedded either on the surface or in the interior of a uniform orthotropic material with properties equal to the composite effective properties. For example, for the case of S2 glass/epoxy composites, the composite effective elastic properties given in Table 2 (estimated using the composite cylinders assemblage model, ref. (25)) were assigned to the infinite material supporting the fiber. Note that despite the composite anisotropy, all of the moduli exceed those of the unreinforced matrix. Hence, in this analysis, the presence of adjacent fibers is expected to increase the lateral support and therefore increase the critical microbuckling strain for the single fiber. The numerical results confirm this expectation. The critical strains computed by the numerical model for a single fiber supported by a uniform material with effective composite properties are significantly higher than the estimates for the dilute case discussed above. For instance, for $V_f = 0.6$, the surface fiber in an S2 glass/epoxy composite buckles at a strain $\epsilon = 0.224$ with a very short microbuckle wavelength ($L = 2.7$). An interior fiber buckles at a strain level $\epsilon = 0.329$ with a microbuckle half-wavelength, $L = 2.0$. These calculated strain levels exceed the experimental values (see Table 3) by more than an order of magnitude. Clearly, modeling composite microbuckling as a single fiber on a foundation with composite effective properties does not give realistic predictions.

Finally, the multiple fiber microbuckling model was exercised for the case $E_f/E_m = 50$ and $V_f = 0.5$. For this case, the Rosen shear mode prediction gives $\epsilon_{cr} = 0.0392$. As discussed above, the mesh length and width was varied to determine the critical strain for the limiting case $L_m \rightarrow \infty$ and $W_m \rightarrow \infty$. Partial deformed mesh plots for the infinite and semi-infinite cases are shown in Figs. 5a and 5b, respectively. Recall that in the infinite case, the fibers are constrained to have the

same deformation while in the semi-infinite case, fibers near the surface are allowed to deform independently. As a result, note that the buckle mode shape for the surface fibers is slightly different than that for interior fibers. As shown in Figs. 6a and 6b, the infinite composite critical strain levels approach the Rosen prediction as the mesh length and width becomes sufficiently large. In the semi-infinite case (Fig. 7a), a similar trend is exhibited with the limiting case $L_m \rightarrow \infty$ and $W_m \rightarrow \infty$ yields a critical strain, $\epsilon_{cr} = 0.0378$ (approximately 2% lower than the corresponding infinite composite case). The effect of varying the number of unconstrained surface fibers is shown in Fig. 7b, where it can be seen that approximately 20 unconstrained surface fibers are needed to model a semi-infinite composite.

5. CONCLUSIONS

In considering the microbuckling of composites with very low fiber volume fractions, the numerical results indicate that for typical composite constituent properties (such as S2 glass/epoxy), microbuckling of both surface and interior fibers occurs at very high strain levels and is therefore not expected to be the dominant failure mechanism. For the case of surface fiber microbuckling in composites with finite fiber volume fractions, two approaches are evaluated. In one approach, the surface fiber is imagined to be supported by a homogeneous elastic foundation with composite effective properties. With this idealization, the numerical model yields compressive failure strains much greater than both experimental values and theoretical predictions for infinite (no free edges) composites. In the other approach to composite microbuckling, a multiple fiber model demonstrates interactions between neighboring fibers significantly reduces the stability of an infinite composite. Furthermore, the reduced lateral support near a free edge also reduces the structural stability and leads to slight reductions in the critical microbuckling strain level.

6. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Discussions with F. C. Spicola and N. DuBois and support from the ASEE Summer Faculty Fellowship Program are gratefully acknowledged.

7. REFERENCES

1. Budiansky, B., "Micromechanics," Symposium on Advances and Trends in Structural and Solid Mechanics, October, 1982.
2. Camponeshi, E. T., "Compression Testing of Thick-Section Composite Materials," unpublished report, 1989.
3. Chung, W. Y. and Testa, R. B., *J. Comp. Mat.*, Vol. 3, 1969, pp. 58-80.
4. Greszczuk, L. B., *ALAA Journal*, Vol. 13, No. 10, October, 1975, pp. 1311-1318.
5. Greszczuk, L. B., *ALAA Journal*, Vol. 9, No. 7, July, 1971, pp. 1274-1280.
6. Hahn, H. T. and Williams, J. G., ASTM STP 893, ASTM, 1986, pp. 115-139.
7. Hermann, L. R. et al, *J. Comp. Mat.*, Vol. 1, 1967, pp. 212-226.
8. Lagoudas, D. C., Tadjbakhsh, I., and Fares, N., "A New Approach to Microbuckling of Fiber Composites," Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute, 1990.
9. Lanir, Y. and Fung, Y. C. B., *J. of Comp. Mat.*, Vol. 6, July, 1972, pp. 387-401.
10. Rosen, B. W., *Fiber Composite Materials*, American Society for Metals, pp. 37-75.
11. Steif, P. S., *Int. J. Solids Structures*, Vol. 23, No. 9, 1987, pp. 1235-1246.
12. Sadowsky, M. A., Pu, S. L., and Hussain, M. A., *J. Appl. Mech.*, Dec. 1967, pp. 1011-1016.
13. Scheurch, H., *ALAA Journal*, Vol. 4, No. 1, January, 1966, pp. 102-106.

14. Spicola, F. C. and DuBois, N. J., ASME International Conference on Computers in Engineering Conference, Boston, MA, August, 1990.
15. Waas, A. M., et al, *J. of Appl. Mech.*, Vol. 57, March, 1990, pp. 138-149.
16. Yeh, J. R. and Teply, J. L., *J. Comp. Mat.*, Vol. 22, March, 1988, pp. 245-257.
17. Shuart, M. J., NASA-TM-87640, Nov., 1985.
18. Camponeshi, E. T., "Compression of Composite Materials: A Review," David Taylor Research Center, DTRC-87/050, November, 1987.
19. Evans, A. G. and Adler, W. F., *Acta Metall.*, Vol. 26, 1978, pp. 725-738.
20. Hahn, H. T. and Williams, J. G., NASA TM-85834, 1986.
21. Sohi, M. S., Hahn, H. T. and Williams, J. G., NASA TM-87604, 1984.
22. Timoshenko, S. P. and Gere, J. M., *Theory of Elastic Stability*, 2nd edition, McGraw-Hill, New York, 1961, pp. 94-98.
23. Cook, R. D., *Concepts and Applications of Finite Element Analysis*, John Wiley & Sons, New York, 1981, pp. 331-346.
24. Taggart D. G., "Numerical Modeling of Microbuckling Failure in Composite Materials" University of Rhode Island, August, 1990.
25. Hashin, Z. and Rosen, B. W., *J. Appl. Mech.*, Vol. 31, 1964, pp. 223-232.

Table 1. S2 Glass Fiber / Epoxy Matrix Composite
Constituent Properties

	S2 Glass Fiber	Epoxy Matrix
Young's Modulus, MPa	85.5	3.4
Poisson's Ratio	0.3	0.3
Shear Modulus, MPa	32.9	1.3

Table 2. Estimated S2 Glass/
Epoxy Effective Composite
Properties - $V_f=0.6$

Axial Modulus, MPa	52.6
Transverse Modulus, MPa	7.57
Axial Poissons Ratio	0.28
Shear Modulus, GPa	4.75

Table 3. S2 Glass/Epoxy Unidirectional Composite Compression
Strength Properties (Ref. 2)

	48 Ply (64 mm)	96 Ply (127 mm)
Compressive Strength, MPa	1280.	976.
Strain to Failure	0.0256	0.0206

a) Interior fiber
b) Surface fiber
Figure 1. Typical mesh geometries for single fiber microbuckling.

a) Mesh used to estimate wavelength
b) Single wavelength mesh length
(mesh length = 19.5 x fiber thickness)
Figure 2. Deformed mesh geometries for surface fiber microbuckle ($E_f/E_m = 100$).

Figure 3. Effect of constituent moduli ratio on microbuckle strain level.

Figure 4. Effect of constituent moduli ratio on microbuckle half-wavelength.

Figure 5. Deformed mesh geometries for a) infinite composite and b) semi-infinite composite

a) Effect of mesh width

b) Effect of mesh length

Figure 6. Effect of mesh width and length on infinite composite critical microbuckling strain.

Figure 7. Effect of a) mesh width (10 unconstrained surface fibers) and b) number of unconstrained surface fibers on semi-infinite composite critical microbuckling strain.